

Valorization of CH₄ emissions into high-added-value products: Assessing the production of ectoine coupled with CH₄ abatement

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Abstract:

This study assessed an innovative strategy for the valorization of dilute methane emissions based on the bio-conversion of CH₄ (the second most important greenhouse gas (GHG)) into ectoine by the methanotrophic ectoine-producing strain *Methylobacterium alcaliphilum* 20 Z. The influence of CH₄ (2-20 %), Cu²⁺ (0.05-50 μM) and NaCl (0-9 %) concentration as well as temperature (25-35 °C) on ectoine synthesis and specific CH₄ biodegradation rate was evaluated for the first time. Concentrations of 20 % CH₄ (at 3 % NaCl, 0.05 μM Cu²⁺, 25 °C) and 6 % NaCl (at 4 % CH₄, 0.05 μM Cu²⁺, 25 °C) supported the maximum intra-cellular ectoine production yield (31.0 ± 1.7 and 66.9 ± 4.2 mg g biomass⁻¹, respectively). On the other hand, extra-cellular ectoine concentrations of up to 4.7 ± 0.1 mg L⁻¹ were detected at high Cu²⁺ concentrations (50 μM), despite this methanotroph has not been previously classified as an ectoine-excreting strain. This research demonstrated the feasibility of the bio-conversion of dilute emissions of methane into high-added value products in an attempt to develop a sustainable GHG bioeconomy.

Keywords: Ectoine, Greenhouse Gas, Methane treatment, Methane biorefinery

1. Introduction

Methane (CH₄) is the second most important greenhouse gas (GHG) emitted nowadays as a result of its high global warming potential (25 times higher than that of CO₂) and emission

rates (United States Environmental Protection Agency, 2015). Despite CH₄ can be used as an energy vector for electricity and heat generation when concentrations are higher than 20 %, more than 56 % of anthropogenic CH₄ emissions worldwide contain concentrations lower than 5 %. When applied to these dilute emissions (such as exhaust gases from landfills or coal mines), current CH₄ abatement technologies are neither environmentally friendly nor cost-effective (Avalos Ramirez et al., 2012).

Nowadays, the lack of a suitable approach to prevent the adverse environmental effects of CH₄ has encouraged both political initiatives to control these GHG emissions and an intensive research on novel strategies for CH₄ abatement (European Environmental Agency, 2015). In this regard, the biological abatement of dilute CH₄ emissions combined with the production of high-added value products represents, if properly tailored, a cost-effective alternative to mitigate CH₄ emissions. This CH₄ bio-refinery approach would avoid the negative environmental effects of methane emissions while turning its treatment into a profitable process.

Ectoine (1,4,5,6-tetrahydro-2-methyl-4-pyrimidinecarboxylic acid) is one of the most valuable microbial protective compounds against osmotic dehydration, as well as an efficient stabilizer for enzymes and nucleic acids (Pastor et al., 2010). This compound has attracted recent attention based on the high retail value that purified ectoine reaches in the cosmetic industry (approximately \$1300 kg⁻¹) (Strong et al., 2015). In 1999, Khmelenina et al. demonstrated that some moderate halophilic methanotrophs such as *Methylobacterium alcaliphilum* 20Z were able to produce and accumulate ectoine inside the cell (But et al., 2013; Kaluzhnaya et al., 2001; Kalyuzhnaya et al., 2008; N. V. Khmelenina et al., 2000; Khmelenina et al., 1999). These studies, conducted at high CH₄ concentrations, represented

the first proof of the ability of CH₄-oxidizing bacteria to produce ectoine. However, little is known about the influence of environmental conditions on the bioproduction of this secondary metabolite when combined with the abatement of dilute CH₄ emissions. Furthermore, no studies on the production of extra-cellular ectoine (naturally excreted to the medium by specific excreting strains) by methanotrophs have been carried out to date.

The present study aimed at systematically elucidating the influence of CH₄, copper (Cu²⁺) and NaCl concentrations, as well as temperature, on the extra and intra-cellular ectoine production using the strain *Methylobacterium alcaliphilum* 20Z.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Chemicals and mineral salt medium

The mineral salt medium (MSM) used was a modified Brunner medium prepared according to Kalyuzhnaya et al. (2008) with a final pH of 9.1. NaCl and CuCl₂·2H₂O were supplemented to the MSM at the different concentrations tested. All chemicals and reagents were purchased from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain) with a purity higher than 99.0 %. CH₄ was purchased from Abello-Linde, S.A. (Barcelona, Spain) with a purity of at least 99.5 %.

2.2. Microorganisms and inoculum preparation

The methanotrophic strain used in this study, *Methylobacterium alcaliphilum* 20Z (Kalyuzhnaya et al., 2008), was purchased from DSMZ (Leibniz-Institut). *Methylobacterium alcaliphilum* 20Z is an halophilic alkalitolerant methanotrophic strain able to produce ectoine in the presence of NaCl (V. N. Khmelenina et al., 2000). Briefly, a 10× dilution of the liquid *Methylobacterium alcaliphilum* 20Z stock culture from DSMZ

was grown at 25 °C in 120 mL glass bottles containing 90 mL of MSM at 3 % of NaCl and 0.05 μM Cu^{2+} . The bottles were closed with gas-tight butyl septa and metallic caps and 50 % v/v of the air headspace was replaced by CH_4 . The inoculum was ready to use in the batch cultivation tests when a bacterial biomass concentration of $0.1 \pm 0.06 \text{ g L}^{-1}$ was achieved.

2.3. Batch cultivation tests

Five series of 13-day tests (TS) were performed in duplicate to evaluate the influence of different environmental factors (CH_4 , NaCl, Cu^{2+} , T) on the production of extra and intracellular ectoine by *Methylobacterium alcaliphilum* 20 Z (Table 1). Sterile batch gas-tight reactors (1.2 L) containing 190 mL of MSM and inoculated with 10 mL of the inoculum above described (to an initial concentration of $0.05 \pm 0.001 \text{ g L}^{-1}$) were used in each tests series. The reactors were closed with gas-tight butyl septa and plastic screw caps. Unless otherwise specified, all tests were initially supplied with a CH_4 headspace concentration of $25 \text{ g CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3}$ (4 %), 3 % of NaCl, 0.05 μM Cu^{2+} and incubated at 25 °C under a continuous magnetic agitation of 600 rpm. All tests were periodically monitored until complete CH_4 consumption, with no replacement of the headspace along the test. The parameter evaluated in each specific test series was: TS1: methane concentration (2, 4 and 20 %), TS2: copper concentration (0.05, 25 and 50 μM), TS3: NaCl concentration (0, 3, 6 and 9 %), and TS4: temperature (25, 30, 35 °C). A final test (TS5) combining the optimum conditions for ectoine production obtained in the previous test series (20 % CH_4 , 50 μM Cu^{2+} , 6 % NaCl and 30 °C) was also carried out.

<Table 1>

Table 1. Cultivation conditions evaluated during *Methylobacterium alcaliphilum* 20Z batch cultivation tests.

Test series (TS)	Operating conditions			
	CH ₄ (%)	Cu ²⁺ (μM)	NaCl (%)	T (°C)
TS1	2, 4, 20	0.05	3	25
TS2	20	0.05, 25, 50	3	25
TS3	20	0.05	0, 3, 6, 9	25
TS4	20	0.05	3	25, 30, 35
TS5	20	50	6	30

Aliquots of pure CH₄ were supplied to the headspace of the reactors in TS1 using a 100 mL gas tight syringe. Copper and NaCl were supplied by addition of the corresponding amount of salt to the cultivation broths in TS2 and TS3, respectively, while the different temperatures used in TS4 (25, 30 or 35° C) were maintained using thermostatic baths (Digiterm-S-150 20).

The O₂, CO₂ and CH₄ headspace concentrations were daily monitored. Aliquots of 10 mL from the cultivation broth were also daily drawn with a liquid syringe to determine biomass concentration and the intra and extra-cellular ectoine concentration. Biomass concentration was estimated via culture absorbance (OD) measurements at 650 nm, which were previously correlated to dry biomass concentrations (g L⁻¹) determined as total suspended solids (TSS) concentration (TSS = 0.30×OD). A cell viability assay was performed in the cultivation of the tests incubated with Cu²⁺ at 25 μM

2.4 Extraction and Analysis of Ectoine

The intra-cellular ectoine concentration was determined using 2 mL of cultivation broth centrifuged at 9000 g and 4 °C for 15 min. Then, 2 mL of 80 % ethanol and 25 ± 5 mg of 0.1-mm-diameter zirconia/silica beads (BioSpec, Spain) were added to the Eppendorf tube containing the pellet. Microbial cells were then disrupted in a Mini-BeadBeater-16 (BioSpec, Spain) at 1048 g for 1 min and the suspension was kept overnight at room temperature (modified from Lang et al., 2011). The supernatant of these suspensions was used for ectoine analysis prior centrifugation at 9000 g and 4 °C for 15 min and filtration through 0.22 μ M filters (Filter-lab, Barcelona). The specific intra-cellular ectoine concentration ($\text{g ectoine g biomass}^{-1}$) was calculated using the TSS concentration (g L^{-1}) of the corresponding cultivation broth. An aliquot of 1 mL of cultivation broth was also drawn and filtered through 0.22 μ M filters (Filter-lab, Barcelona) to measure the extra-cellular ectoine concentration. The concentration of ectoine was measured by HPLC-UV in a HPLC 717 plus auto-sampler (Waters, Bellefonte, USA) coupled with a UV Dual λ Absorbance detector (Waters, Bellefonte, USA detector) at 220 nm using a LC-18 AQ + C Supelcosil column (Waters, Bellefonte, EEUU) and a C18 AQ + pre-column (Waters, Bellefonte, EEUU). A phosphate buffer, consisting of 0.8 mM K_2HPO_4 and 6.0 mM Na_2HPO_4 , was used as a mobile phase at 25 °C and a flow rate of 1 mL min^{-1} (Becker et al., 2013). Ectoine quantification was carried out using external standards of commercially available ectoine ((S)-b-2-methyl-1,4,5,6-tetrahydro-pyrimidine-4-carboxylic acid, purity 95 %, Sigma Aldrich, Spain) (Tanimura et al., 2013). The detection and quantification limits (DL and QL) were calculated via determination of the signal-to-noise ratio performed by comparing the measured signals from samples with known low concentrations of analyte with those of blank samples. This procedure allowed establishing the minimum concentration at which the analyte can be reliably detected. A signal-to-noise ratio between 3:1 and 2:1 is generally

considered acceptable for estimating the detection limit while a signal-to-noise ratio of 10:1 is necessary to determine the quantification limit (ICH Expert working Group, 2005).

2.5 Analytical procedures

CH₄, O₂ and CO₂ gas concentrations were determined in a Bruker 430 GC-TCD (Palo Alto, USA) equipped with a CP-Molsieve 5A (15 m × 0.53 μm × 15 μm) and a CP-PoraBOND Q (25 m × 0.53 μm × 10 μm) column. The oven, injector and detector temperatures were maintained at 45 °C, 150 °C and 200 °C, respectively. Helium was used as the carrier gas at 13.7 mL min⁻¹.

Culture absorbance measurements at 650 nm were conducted using a Shimadzu UV-2550 UV/Vis spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan). TSS concentration was measured according to standard methods (American Water Works Association, 2012). Vital and dead bacteria were identified using the LIVE/DEAD BacLight™ Bacterial Viability Kit (L13152) using a Leica DM4000B microscope equipped with a Leica DFC300FX.

2.6. Data analysis

The specific CH₄ degradation rate (SDR, g CH₄ g⁻¹_{biomass} h⁻¹) was calculated from the slope of the time course plot of methane concentration within the linear range in the batch cultivation tests carried out. The statistical data analysis was performed using SPSS 20.0 (IBM, USA). The results are given as the average ± standard deviation. The homogeneity of the variance of the parameters was evaluated using a Levene test. Significant differences were analysed by ANOVA and post-hoc analysis for multiple group comparisons. Differences were considered to be significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

3. Results

3.1. Influence of cultivation conditions on intra-cellular ectoine production

Intra-cellular ectoine reached its maximum concentration between days 5 and 7 of cultivation regardless of the conditions tested. Subsequently, the concentration of intra-cellular ectoine remained constant until the end of the assay (Figure 1a). No significant difference was recorded in the intra-cellular ectoine concentration at 4 % CH₄, 3 % NaCl, 0.05 μM Cu²⁺ and 25 °C in TS1-TS4, which confirmed the reproducibility and consistency of the results here obtained. Both CH₄ and NaCl concentrations had a significant influence on the production of intra-cellular ectoine (Figure 2). A CH₄ concentration of 20 % supported maximum specific yields of 31.0 ± 1.7 mg ectoine g biomass⁻¹ by the end of the cultivation, while the maximum yields obtained at CH₄ concentrations of 2 and 4 % were 9.9 ± 0.6 and 13.6 ± 3.8 mg ectoine g biomass⁻¹, respectively. A NaCl concentration of 6 % was identified as the optimum value for the accumulation of intra-cellular ectoine, which reached a maximum concentration of 66.9 ± 4.2 mg ectoine g biomass⁻¹. Higher or lower salt concentrations supported lower ectoine yields (30.4 ± 7.5 mg ectoine g biomass⁻¹ at 9 % NaCl; 12.5 ± 3.9 mg ectoine g biomass⁻¹ at 3 % NaCl; 1.2 ± 0.5 mg ectoine g biomass⁻¹ at 0 % NaCl). On the contrary, no significant effect ($p < 0.05$) of temperature or Cu²⁺ concentration was observed on the production of intra-cellular ectoine (Figure 2).

<Figure 1>

Figure 1. Time course of the concentration of CH₄ (●, continuous line), CO₂ (■, dotted line). DO_x100 (dashed and dotted line) and intra-cellular (a) or extra-cellular (b) ectoine

(▲, dashed line) at a) during *Methylobacterium alcaliphilum* 20Z cultivation at 6 % NaCl, 0.05 μM Cu^{2+} , 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 4 % CH_4 , and b) at 3 % NaCl, 50 μM Cu^{2+} , 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 4 % CH_4 .

<Figure 2>

Figure 2. Maximum intra-cellular ectoine yield under different cultivation conditions. Vertical lines represent standard deviations from replicates. Columns inter/intra-groups with different letters were significantly different at $p < 0.05$.

The maximum specific intra-cellular ectoine yields recorded at the different Cu^{2+} concentrations tested were 12.0 ± 2.6 mg ectoine g biomass⁻¹ at 0.05 μM Cu^{2+} , 10.3 ± 0.5 mg ectoine g biomass⁻¹ at 25 μM Cu^{2+} and 12.4 ± 0.7 mg ectoine g biomass⁻¹ at 50 μM Cu^{2+} . Similarly, no significant effect of temperature on ectoine accumulation was observed within the tested T range, with an average yield of 11.70 ± 1.1 mg ectoine g biomass⁻¹.

3.2. Influence of cultivation conditions on ectoine excretion

While no extra-cellular ectoine was detected (DL= 0.4 mg/L and QL= 0.65 mg/L) during the 13 days of cultivation under the different concentrations of CH₄, NaCl and temperature tested, ectoine excretion was detected at high Cu²⁺ concentration (Figure 3).

<Figure 3>

Figure 3. Extra-cellular ectoine excreted under different cultivation conditions. Vertical lines represent standard deviations from replicates. Columns inter/intra-groups with different letters were significantly different at $p < 0.05$.

Ectoine excretion was observed by day 4 in tests supplemented with high Cu²⁺ concentrations (Figure 1b). The maximum concentrations recorded were 0.7 ± 0.05 and 1.2

± 0.01 mg extra-cellular ectoine L^{-1} (0.5 and 1.1 % ($g\ g^{-1}$)) at 25 and 50 μM of Cu^{2+} , respectively.

3.3. Influence of cultivation conditions on the specific CH_4 degradation rate

In the TS1 (0.05 μM Cu^{2+} , 3 % NaCl and 25°C), the results showed that a CH_4 headspace concentration of 20 % supported a significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher SDR ($1.50 \pm 0.08\ g\ CH_4\ h^{-1}\ g\ biomass^{-1}$) compared to the SDRs recorded at 4 and 2 % of CH_4 (0.33 ± 0.05 and $0.29 \pm 0.03\ g\ CH_4\ h^{-1}\ g\ biomass^{-1}$, respectively) (Figure 4). The results showed that a CH_4 headspace concentration of 20 % supported a significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher SDR ($1.50 \pm 0.08\ g\ CH_4\ h^{-1}\ g\ biomass^{-1}$) compared to the SDRs recorded at 4 and 2 % of CH_4 (0.33 ± 0.05 and $0.29 \pm 0.03\ g\ CH_4\ h^{-1}\ g\ biomass^{-1}$, respectively) (Figure 4). On the contrary, the specific CH_4 oxidation rates decreased at higher NaCl concentrations, with CH_4 SDRs of 0.05 ± 0.005 , 0.22 ± 0.02 , 0.34 ± 0.02 and $0.38 \pm 0.02\ g\ CH_4\ h^{-1}\ g\ biomass^{-1}$ at 9, 6, 3 and 0 % NaCl, respectively. Neither temperature (25, 30 and 35 °C supported SDRs of 0.34 ± 0.04 , 0.30 ± 0.01 and $0.30 \pm 0.01\ g\ CH_4\ h^{-1}\ g\ biomass^{-1}$, respectively) nor Cu^{2+} concentration (0.05, 25 and 50 μM of Cu^{2+} supported SDRs of 0.35 ± 0.01 , 0.43 ± 0.01 and $0.37 \pm 0.05\ g\ CH_4\ h^{-1}\ g\ biomass^{-1}$, respectively) showed a significant effect on the specific CH_4 degradation rate.

<Figure 4>

Figure 4. Specific CH₄ biodegradation rate under different cultivation conditions. Vertical lines represent standard deviations from replicates. Columns inter/intra-groups with different letters were significantly different at $p < 0.05$.

3.4. Production of extra and intra-cellular ectoine under optimum cultivation conditions

A final study was carried out combining the optimum parameters from previous tests TS1-TS4 in order to determine the production of extra and intra-cellular ectoine (20 % CH₄, 6 % NaCl, 30 °C, 50 µM Cu²⁺) (Table 2). These cultivation conditions promoted the excretion of ectoine to the extra-cellular medium (4.7 mg L⁻¹, which would correspond to 33.3 mg ectoine g biomass⁻¹) and resulted in a high production of intra-cellular ectoine (40.7 ± 0.02 mg ectoine g biomass⁻¹).

<Table 2>

Table 2. Maximum values of ectoine concentration and specific CH₄ degradation rates for each test

	Maximum extra-cellular ectoine		Maximum intra-cellular ectoine		Maximum specific CH ₄ degradation rate
	[Ectoine] (mg L ⁻¹)	% Ectoine ((g Ect. g biomass ⁻¹) ×100)	[Ectoine] (mg g biomass ⁻¹)	% Ectoine ((g Ect. g biomass ⁻¹) ×100)	(g CH ₄ h ⁻¹ g biomass ⁻¹)
TS1					
20% CH ₄ , 25°C, 0.05μM Cu ²⁺ , 3% NaCl	N/D	N/D	31.0 ± 1.7	3.1 %	1.50 ± 0.08
TS2					
4% CH ₄ , 25°C, 0.05μM Cu ²⁺ , 6% NaCl	N/D	N/D	66.9 ± 4.2	6.7 %	0.22 ± 0.02
TS3					
4% CH ₄ , 25°C, 50μM Cu ²⁺ , 3% NaCl	1.2 ± 0.01	1.1 %	12.4 ± 0.7	1.2 %	0.30 ± 0.01
TS4					
4% CH ₄ , 30°C, 0.05μM Cu ²⁺ , 3% NaCl	N/D	N/D	10.6 ± 0.15	1.1 %	0.37 ± 0.05
TS5					
20 % CH ₄ , 30°C, 50μM Cu ²⁺ , 6% NaCl	4.7 ± 0.05	3.2 %	40.7 ± 0.02	4.1 %	2.03 ± 0.11

4. Discussion

This research investigated for the first time the effect of 4 environmental parameters (i.e. CH₄ concentration, Cu²⁺ concentration, temperature and NaCl concentration) on the production and excretion of ectoine and on the specific CH₄ degradation by *Methylobacterium alcaliphilum* 20 Z in order to elucidate the optimum operational conditions to maximize ectoine production during the abatement of dilute CH₄ emissions.

A high concentration of CH₄ in the GHG emission significantly enhanced the production of intra-cellular ectoine likely due to an increase in substrate availability for the bacterial community, which induced high growth rates and therefore a high metabolite production (Estrada et al., 2014). In this sense, an increase in CH₄ concentration from 4 to 20 % enhanced the production of intra-cellular ectoine by a factor of 2.7 (from 9.9 ± 0.6 to 30.4 ± 7.5 mg ectoine g biomass⁻¹). However, no significant effect was observed on the accumulation of ectoine within the lower range of CH₄ concentrations tested (2 and 4 %). The key role of CH₄ concentration in the intra-cellular ectoine accumulation is in agreement with the results observed by Khmelenina et al. (2000), who recorded a maximum ectoine concentration of 200 mg ectoine g biomass⁻¹ in *Methylobacterium alcaliphilum* 20 Z under a CH₄ concentration of 50 % (v/v) in a MSM with 6 % of NaCl, 0.05 μM Cu²⁺ at 29 °C (V. N. Khmelenina et al., 2000; Trotsenko et al., 2005). However, only dilute CH₄ emissions (<20 %) not suitable for energy recovery can be considered as a substrate of this novel CH₄ bio-refinery.

The salinity of the cultivation medium exhibited a positive effect on the intra-cellular ectoine yield up to a concentration of 6 % NaCl (66.9 ± 4.2 mg ectoine g biomass⁻¹). The

same effect has been observed by other authors using *Methylomicrobium alcaliphilum* 20Z. For instance, But et al. (2013) observed a 4 times increase in the concentration of intracellular ectoine in *M. alcaliphilum* 20Z when salt concentration was raised from 3 to 7 % (from 10 to 40 $\mu\text{g mg biomass}^{-1}$). However, in our particular study, higher salt concentrations resulted in lower ectoine yields ($30.4 \pm 7.5 \text{ mg ectoine g biomass}^{-1}$ at 9 % of NaCl).

Some authors have also observed a decrease in ectoine accumulation at increasing external salinity due to the regulation of the ectoine biosynthesis at the enzyme activity level (Reshetnikov et al., 2005). It is noteworthy that the concentration of ectoine herein obtained at 6 % NaCl does not differ much from the values commonly encountered during the industrial production of ectoine using the glucose fermentative microorganism *Halomonas elongate* (yielding ectoine at an average value of $155.5 \text{ mg ectoine g biomass}^{-1}$ when reused 9 times) (Strong et al., 2015). Nowadays, the process implemented at industrial scale (bacterial milking) involves the cyclic increase and decrease of the salt concentration in the cultivation broth up to 12 % NaCl. This process involving salt shocks increases reactor corrosion and hinders the downstream processing of ectoine due to the discontinuous nature of the production procedure and the high concentrations of salt. Moreover, this process requires an expensive carbon source such as glucose. Alternatively, *Methylomicrobium alcaliphilum* 20Z can continuously synthesize a comparable high yield of ectoine in a less harsh cultivation medium coupled with CH_4 abatement from dilute emissions, which lowers production costs and mitigates climate change. Ectoine production was also observed in the absence of NaCl, although the concentrations detected were 55 times lower than the maximum ectoine yield recorded at 6 % of NaCl. The presence of a basal activity of the

specific enzymes responsible for ectoine biosynthesis was likely related to the constitutive transcription of the ectoine gene cluster by this strain as previously observed by Khmelenina et al. (2000) and Reshetnikov et al. (2006). Moreover, the high concentration of sodium carbonates present in the cultivation media could have mediated the expression of the *ectabc* operon.

Likewise, Reshetnikov et al. (2006) confirmed that the optimum temperature for the enzymes catalyzing the key reactions of ectoine biosynthesis in *Methylobacterium alcaliphilum* 20Z was 20 °C, while temperatures higher than 30 °C inhibited this reaction. However, no pernicious effect of temperature on the production of intra-cellular ectoine was observed in the present study. Moreover, no significant differences occurred among the ectoine yields recorded in the cultivation media containing different Cu^{2+} concentrations.

Ectoine excreting bacterial strains can accumulate ectoine and excrete it into the cultivation medium, thus enhancing the economics of the industrial production process of ectoine (Lang et al., 2011). Up to date, *Methylobacterium alcaliphilum* 20Z has never been described as a strain able to excrete ectoine to the extra-cellular medium (Trotsenko et al., 2005). Whereas no extra-cellular ectoine was detected at the concentrations of NaCl and CH_4 and temperatures tested, cultivation at high Cu^{2+} concentrations promoted the excretion of a significant fraction of intra-cellular ectoine. This excretion could be have been caused by a release from dead or injured cells by Cu^{2+} . However, no significant differences were observed among the final biomass concentrations or SDR recorded under the three Cu^{2+} concentrations tested (Figure 1. Supplementary Materials). Moreover, a cell viability assay of *Methylobacterium alcaliphilum* 20Z grown at high copper concentrations demonstrated that this element was not toxic (Figure 2, Supplementary

Materials). In this regard, copper could be associated with the activation of unspecific channels or specific transporters able to excrete ectoine as a result of passive diffusion or an active transport of the cation Cu^{2+} . A research carried out by Schubert et al. (2007) observed that a transgenic *E.coli* genetically modified with the genes for ectoine biosynthesis, *ectABC*, from the halophilic bacterium *Chromohalobacter salexigens*, was able to excrete ectoine via expression of a specific transporter (Schubert et al., 2007). In this context, the presence of high Cu^{2+} concentrations in the cultivation medium could affect the activation of some specific transporters. Gram negative bacteria can express the tubular trans-membrane proteins porins, which allow the diffusion of small solutes and constitute a likely route for the simultaneous uptake of unchelated Cu^{2+} and excretion of intra-cellular ectoine in methanotrophs (Balasubramanian et al., 2011).

Along with the optimization of ectoine production, the maintenance of an efficient CH_4 abatement from dilute emissions of this GHG is also of key importance in the context of climate change mitigation. Hence, the highest SDRs were obtained at a CH_4 concentration of 20 % as a result of the enhanced gas-liquid concentration gradients, which likely induced higher aqueous CH_4 concentrations and therefore higher specific growth rates (Figure 3. Supplementary Materials) (Cantera et al., 2016). However, no SDR enhancement was observed in the low range of CH_4 concentrations (2 and 4 %), as previously reported by Cantera et al. (2016). The complete oxidation of 1 mol of CH_4 requires a maximum of 2 mol of O_2 , this ratio being lower in practice as a result of biomass growth. On the one hand, the K_{La} of O_2 and CH_4 are relatively similar, which means that the transfer of oxygen and methane from the gas phase to the microbial community is a function of their concentration in the gas phase (Yu et al., 2006). On the other hand, our particular study focused on the

treatment of dilute CH₄ emissions, where the concentration of oxygen is typically larger than the concentration of CH₄ (> 20%) and O₂ limitation is unlikely to occur. On the other hand, high salt concentrations negatively affected methane biodegradation in *Methylobacterium alcaliphilum* 20Z, the SDR obtained at 9 % NaCl being 7.7 times lower than that obtained at 3 % NaCl. This strain is an halotolerant alkaliphilic methanotroph (Khmelenina et al., 1997) that can tolerate higher salt concentrations than other methanotrophs, but highly saline environments are not its optimum habitat. Thus, despite higher NaCl concentrations mediated the highest ectoine yields (6 and 9 %), a reduced CH₄ abatement performance was recorded. On the other hand, temperature and Cu²⁺ did not affect the SDR.

Finally, the optimum conditions (30°C, 50 µM Cu²⁺, 20 % of CH₄ and 6 % of NaCl) were combined in a test in order to maximize both extra and intra-cellular ectoine production. In this particular assay, the production of extra-cellular ectoine was 4 times higher than that obtained in TS2 (25°C, 50 µM Cu²⁺, 4 % of CH₄ and 3 % of NaCl), while the intra-cellular ectoine yield was lower than that recorded in TS3 (6 % of NaCl, 0.05 µM Cu²⁺ and 4 % of CH₄). Thus, the combination of these parameters favored the excretion of 44.4 % of the total intra-cellular ectoine produced (4.7 % (g g⁻¹)). The total (intra-cellular + extra-cellular) ectoine produced would account for 73 mg ectoine g biomass⁻¹ if not excreted, which was similar to the intracellular ectoine concentration (66.9 ± 4.2 mg gbiomass⁻¹) in TS3 at 6 % NaCl. These concentrations were lower than those reported by other ectoine producing strains grown on costly high-quality carbon sources (e.g. glucose). For example, *Halomonas elongate* has been reported to produce 4.1 g L⁻¹ of extra-cellular ectoine (90% of the total ectoine) in industrial fed-batch fermentation (Sauer and Galinski, 1998), while

Brevibacterium epidermis excretes 8 g L⁻¹ (50% of the total ectoine produced) (Onraedt et al., 2005). However, these systems were operated with a high cell density of 48 and 49 g L⁻¹, respectively, while the biomass concentration maintained in our batch study was ~ 100 mg L⁻¹. Therefore, the specific amount of extra-cellular ectoine here obtained could be comparable with previous industrial studies when expressed as g ectoine per g biomass.

5. Conclusion

A proper selection of the environmental parameters (temperature, Cu²⁺, NaCl and CH₄ concentration) during *Methylomicrobium alcaliphilum* 20Z cultivation is crucial to simultaneously, maximize both the intra-cellular production and excretion of ectoine and CH₄ abatement. The study here presented constitutes a first attempt to evaluate the feasibility of producing ectoine combined with methane abatement. The promising results obtained in this preliminary study support further research in order to implement this CH₄ biorefinery in a continuous system capable of creating value out of GHG mitigation using extremophilic methanotrophs.

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7. References

- American Water Works Association, 2012. Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater, American Water Works Association/American Public Works Association/Water Environment Federation.
- Avalos Ramirez, A., García-Aguilar, B.P., Jones, J.P., Heitz, M., 2012. Improvement of methane biofiltration by the addition of non-ionic surfactants to biofilters packed with inert materials. *Process Biochem.* 47, 76–82.
- Balasubramanian, R., Kenney, G.E., Rosenzweig, A.C., 2011. Dual pathways for copper uptake by methanotrophic bacteria. *J. Biol. Chem.* 286, 37313–37319. doi:10.1074/jbc.M111.284984
- Becker, J., Schäfer, R., Kohlstedt, M., Harder, B.J., Borchert, N.S., Stöveken, N., 2013. Systems metabolic engineering of *Corynebacterium glutamicum* for production of the chemical chaperone ectoine Systems metabolic engineering of *Corynebacterium glutamicum* for production of the chemical chaperone ectoine. *Microb. Cell Fact.* 12, 110–126.
- But, S.Y., Khmelenina, V.N., Mustakhimov, I.I., Trotsenko, Y.A., 2013. Construction and Characterization of *Methylobacterium alcaliphilum* 20Z Knockout Mutants Defective in Sucrose and Ectoine Biosynthesis Genes. *Microbiology* 82, 253–255. doi:10.1134/S0026261713020021
- Cantera, S., Lebrero, R., García-encina, P.A., Mu, R., 2016. Evaluation of the influence of methane and copper concentration and methane mass transport on the community structure and biodegradation kinetics of methanotrophic cultures 171, 11–20. doi:10.1016/j.jenvman.2016.02.002
- Estrada, J.M., Lebrero, R., Quijano, G., Pérez, R., Figueroa-González, I., García-Encina, P.A., Muñoz, R., 2014. Methane abatement in a gas-recycling biotrickling filter: Evaluating innovative operational strategies to overcome mass transfer limitations. *Chem. Eng. J.* 253, 385–393. doi:10.1016/j.cej.2014.05.053
- European Environmental Agency, 2015. Atmospheric greenhouse gas concentrations (CSI 013/CLIM 052) - Assessment published Feb 2015. [WWW Document]. <http://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/indicators/atmospheric-greenhouse-gas-concentrations-4/assessment>.
- ICH, E.W. group, 2005. Validation of analytical procedures: text and methodology q2(r1), in: international

conference on harmonisation of technical requirements for registration of pharmaceuticals for human use.

- Kaluzhnaya, M., Khmelenina, V., Eshinimaev, B., Suzina, N., Nikitin, D., Solonin, a, Lin, J.L., McDonald, I., Murrell, C., Trotsenko, Y., 2001. Taxonomic characterization of new alkaliphilic and alkalitolerant methanotrophs from soda lakes of the Southeastern Transbaikal region and description of *Methylomicrobium buryatense* sp.nov. *Syst. Appl. Microbiol.* 24, 166–176. doi:10.1078/0723-2020-00028
- Kalyuzhnaya, M.G., Khmelenina, V., Eshinimaev, B., Sorokin, D., Fuse, H., Lidstrom, M., Trotsenko, Y., 2008. Classification of halo(alkali)philic and halo(alkali)tolerant methanotrophs provisionally assigned to the genera *Methylomicrobium* and *Methylobacter* and emended description of the genus *Methylomicrobium*. *Int. J. Syst. Evol. Microbiol.* 58, 591–596. doi:10.1099/ijs.0.65317-0
- Khmelenina, N.V., Kalyuzhnaya, G.M., Starostina, G.N., Suzina, E.N., Trotsenko, A.Y., 2000. Isolation and Characterization of Halotolerant Alkaliphilic Methanotrophic Bacteria from Tuva Soda Lakes. *Curr. Microbiol.* 35, 257–261. doi:10.1007/s002849900249
- Khmelenina, V.N., Kalyuzhnaya, M.G., Sakharovsky, V.G., Snzina, N.E., Trotsenko, Y. a., Gottschalk, G., 1999. Osmoadaptation in halophilic and alkaliphilic methanotrophs. *Arch. Microbiol.* 172, 321–329. doi:10.1007/s002030050786
- Khmelenina, V.N., Kalyuzhnaya, M.G., Starostina, N.G., Suzina, N.E., Trotsenko, Y. a., 1997. Isolation and characterization of halotolerant alkaliphilic methanotrophic bacteria from Tuva soda lakes. *Curr. Microbiol.* 35, 257–261. doi:10.1007/s002849900249
- Khmelenina, V.N., Sakharovskii, V.G., Reshetnikov, a S., Trotsenko, I. a, 2000. Synthesis of osmoprotectors by halophilic and alkalophilic methanotrophs. *Mikrobiologiya* 69, 465–470.
- Lang, Y. jun, Bai, L., Ren, Y. nan, Zhang, L. hua, Nagata, S., 2011. Production of ectoine through a combined process that uses both growing and resting cells of *Halomonas salina* DSM 5928T. *Extremophiles* 15, 303–310. doi:10.1007/s00792-011-0360-9
- Onraedt, A.E., Walcarius, B. a., Soetaert, W.K., Vandamme, E.J., 2005. Optimization of ectoine synthesis

- through fed-batch fermentation of *Brevibacterium epidermis*. *Biotechnol. Prog.* 21, 1206–1212.
doi:10.1021/bp0500967
- Pastor, J.M., Salvador, M., Argandoña, M., Bernal, V., Reina-Bueno, M., Csonka, L.N., Iborra, J.L., Vargas, C., Nieto, J.J., Cánovas, M., 2010. Ectoines in cell stress protection: Uses and biotechnological production. *Biotechnol. Adv.* 28, 782–801. doi:10.1016/j.biotechadv.2010.06.005
- Reshetnikov, A.S., Khmelenina, V.N., Trotsenko, Y.A., 2006. Characterization of the ectoine biosynthesis genes of haloalkalotolerant obligate methanotroph “*Methylobacterium alcaliphilum* 20Z.” *Arch. Microbiol.* 184, 286–297. doi:10.1007/s00203-005-0042-z
- Reshetnikov, A.S., Mustakhimov, I.I., Khmelenina, V.N., Trotsenko, Y.A., 2005. Cloning, purification, and characterization of diaminobutyrate acetyltransferase from the halotolerant methanotroph *Methylobacterium alcaliphilum* 20Z. *Biochem.* 70, 878–883. doi:10.1007/s10541-005-0197-x
- Sauer, T., Galinski, E.A., 1998. Bacterial Milking : A Novel Bioprocess for Production of Compatible Solutes. *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* 57, 306–313.
- Schubert, T., Maskow, T., Benndorf, D., Harms, H., Breuer, U., 2007. Continuous synthesis and excretion of the compatible solute ectoine by a transgenic, nonhalophilic bacterium. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 73, 3343–3347. doi:10.1128/AEM.02482-06
- Strong, P., Xie, S., Clarke, W.P., 2015. Methane as a resource: can the methanotrophs add value? *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 49, 4001–4018. doi:10.1021/es504242n
- Tanimura, K., Nakayama, H., Tanaka, T., Kondo, A., 2013. Ectoine production from lignocellulosic biomass-derived sugars by engineered *Halomonas elongata*. *Bioresour. Technol.* 142, 523–529.
doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2013.05.004
- Trotsenko, Y.A., Doronina, N. V., Khmelenina, V.N., 2005. Biotechnological potential of aerobic methylotrophic bacteria: A review of current state and future prospects. *Appl. Biochem. Microbiol.* 41, 433–441. doi:10.1007/s10438-005-0078-5
- United States Environmental Protection Agency., 2013. Global Greenhouse Gas Emissions Data [WWW Document]. United States Environ. Prot. Agency. URL

<http://www.epa.gov/climatechange/ghgemissions/gases/ch4.html>

Yu Y, Ramsay JA, Ramsay BA. 2006. On-Line Estimation of Dissolved Methane Concentration During Methanotrophic Fermentations. *Biotechnology Bioeng.* **95**:788–793.